

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In this article, systematic organization of selection of talented athletes among young people and further development of physical education and mass sports, comprehensive study of children's health during the activity of physical education guides, study of its dynamics, correction of physical and mental health of children, education Pedagogical technologies used by instructors during the training to form appropriate ideas about a healthy lifestyle in students and the methods of their effective use during the training are highlighted.*

Keywords: *innovations, educational technologies, healthy lifestyle, gross motor skills, fine motor skills, physical development, sensorimotor.*

To create a healthy lifestyle in our society, to create conditions for the population, especially the younger generation, for regular physical education and mass sports, to strengthen young people's confidence in their will, strengths and capabilities through sports competitions and courage. and Order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 No. Resolution "Further development of physical education and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 No. 5924 "Pre-school education of youth" in order to ensure the implementation of the second initiative aimed at increasing morale and meaningful organization of their free time - physical education of youth, creating the necessary conditions for them to demonstrate their abilities in the field of sports and information about the work carried out in secondary schools, as well as the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" and on preschool education adopted in 2019, and the basic principles of education and the main directions of state policy in preschool education are explained. It is in order to ensure the implementation of this law that the "First Step" educational program was developed.

Preschool education is a rapidly developing area of education, which is the focus of attention of education specialists and researchers around the world and in our country. Currently, Uzbekistan is undergoing a radical reform of the preschool education system. The state curriculum is aimed at developing a child as a comprehensively developed personality and is the main document defining the goals, objectives, principles, expected results, content and organization of the learning and education process. This document also provides the basis for the development of alternative, partial, adapted preschool education programs.

Interdependent improvement of competencies in areas of development that ensure the comprehensive development of the child, as well as his smooth transition to the next stage, which is school education, and his readiness for it, primary education is necessary for the formation of

competencies in lim. One of the child's competencies: - physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Physical education in kindergarten is an important part of the educational process, which helps children develop physical fitness, coordination, endurance and strength. Sports activities are conducted in the form of games, allowing children to master interesting and new skills.

During physical activity, metabolism accelerates, which promotes active burning of fat cells.

Sport strengthens the immune system and helps resist seasonal colds and viral infections.

Regular physical exercise helps strengthen the spine, which promotes a healthy state and has a positive effect on the functioning of internal organs.

Sport helps strengthen the condition of the cardiovascular system (unless, of course, the child has medical contraindications for performing a standard set of exercises).

The effect of sports activities is strengthening bones and improving oxygen metabolism in the body.

Physical exercise increases cellular metabolism and improves lipid metabolism.

Proper physical activity can help you calm down in stressful situations, improve sleep, and focus on important school tasks during the day.

Goals and objectives of physical education in kindergarten:

development of children's physical qualities and health promotion;

formation of correct posture and improved coordination of actions;

- developing interest in physical education and sports;
- teaching basic motor skills and exercises;
- prevention of diseases of the musculoskeletal system and cardiovascular system;
- development of communication skills and the ability to work in a team;
- instill respect for safety rules in the classroom and in everyday life.

The area "Physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle" is divided into the following sub-sectors:

- gross motor skills;
- fine motor skills;
- sensorimotor;
- healthy lifestyle and safety.

Taking into account the above areas, we need to establish age requirements for children.

The duration of the exercises may vary depending on the age of the child:

1-2 years – no more than five to eight minutes;

3-4 years – 10-15 minutes;

5-6 years – 15-20 minutes.

The main thing during the heat is to ensure that children do not overwork or get tired. And before physical activity, warming up is important. The best way to do this is in the following format:

walking in place or around the hall;

running in place or around the hall;

arms and legs are shaking.

Running and jumping are great aerobic exercise options for children. This type of physical activity helps strengthen your leg muscles and improve your cardiovascular endurance. These

exercises can be performed both at home and on the playground near the kindergarten - they do not require additional equipment. You can run indoors wall-to-wall at an easy pace or compete in the 60-meter relay.

Walking on hands and all fours strengthens the muscles of the arms, back and core. Crawling on all fours is a simple and safe exercise for all ages that works most muscles. It is even more beneficial to walk on your hands, which develops complex coordination and uses underdeveloped muscles of the arms, back and core.

Throwing a ball develops the muscles of the arms and chest. Improves intermuscular coordination, reaction and spatial orientation. Children can throw the ball to each other, roll it on the ground, throw it behind their back and crouch while throwing the ball. You can also throw different sized balls at a basket or target and compete with distance and accuracy. For senior and preparatory groups, you can use balls weighing from 0.5 to 2 kg.

Dance and music classes can also be excellent aerobic exercise for children. Not only are they fun and exciting, but they also help improve coordination, balance and rhythm. These activities can be incorporated into a schedule or used on their own during play or a walk.

Morning exercises

Morning exercises are a set of exercises performed before breakfast. It helps children wake up, recharge their batteries for the day and prepare for active activities.

What is morning exercise? warming; heating;

A set of basic exercises;

The final stage.

The morning exercise complex includes several types of exercises:

warm-up – running in place, swinging your arms and legs;

stretching – bending, twisting, stretching the muscles of the arms, legs and back;

jumping in place or jumping rope;

running in place or in a circle;

breathing exercises - inhale and exhale deeply to improve blood circulation and saturate the body with oxygen.

The order of field development in children aged 0-7 years:

Gross motor skills: The child controls his body and its parts, moves purposefully.

Fine motor skills: The child coordinates and uses his hands and fingers for a variety of purposes.

Sensorimotor: the child is able to control his movements using the senses.

Healthy lifestyle and safety: The child demonstrates health skills and has an understanding of safe, healthy eating and living rules.

During this period, in order to adapt children to a healthy lifestyle and subsequent educational processes, one can expect the development of competencies in the direction of “Physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle”:

After completing educational activities in the direction of “Physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle”, a child 6-7 years old:

exhibits physical activity in accordance with the norms of physical development associated with his capabilities and age;

knows how to harmoniously and purposefully perform various motor actions;

uses fine motor skills in various life and educational situations;

controls his actions with the help of emotional and sensory organs;
uses personal hygiene skills;
knows the basics of a healthy lifestyle and diet;
complies with the rules of the basics of safe life.

Based on these documents and requirements, we can use innovative technologies that we can use when carrying out physical targeting activities:

The priority task in the activities of physical education instructors is a comprehensive study of children's health, study of its dynamics, correction of children's physical and mental health, and formation of students' ideas about a healthy lifestyle.

Pedagogical technologies used by instructors during training include:

Development of pedagogical technologies aimed at revealing the child's motor skills and abilities, encouraging children to engage in independent motor activities related to their needs;

Gaming technologies. The use of properly formed skills and tools, especially games, allows you to understand the tasks that arise in unforeseen situations during the course of activity. Motor skills developed in children under seven years of age are the basis for their further improvement at school, help them master more complex movements and allow them to achieve high results in sports in the future. When working with children we can include:

- games and exercises that develop the ability to identify the main, characteristic features of objects and compare them;
- games that develop self-control, speed of reaction to words, phonemic awareness, intelligence.

Here are some games that can positively affect children's mood:

“Reaching for the sun” Starting position: the child stands, legs slightly apart, arms along the body. Exhale, raise your arms up and stand on your tiptoes. We exhale and lower our arms, returning to full legs.

“Let's say hello to your toes” Starting position: standing, feet shoulder-width apart, arms to the sides. The child exhales and bends on his toes, trying to lower his arms as much as possible.

“Mill” Starting position: feet shoulder-width apart, child leans forward, arms spread to the sides. One hand reaches down and the other rises, inhaling and exhaling.

“Applause” The boy walks around the hall, clapping his hands wider than usual to strengthen the shoulder girdle. He alternately claps in front, above his head and behind.

- Observing animals during training, traveling with fairy-tale characters, imitating Olympic champions, games and entertainment, preschool education. With the help of the above activities, children will acquire the habit of a healthy lifestyle and acquire basic cognitive skills:

1. predicting the consequences of an action or event;
2. check errors and shortcomings in your actions;
3. management of own activities;
4. understand the real situation.

- health-saving technologies aimed at strengthening the physical development and health of the child: the development of his physical qualities, the formation of motor activity and physical culture of preschoolers, the formation of motor activity and physical culture of preschoolers, physical education, breathing exercises, massage and self-massage, recommendations for the prevention of flat feet and correct posture , fitness classes in gyms, daily physical activity and developing habits to maintain health

- Technologies of social and personal development - development of mental and social health of preschool children;

- Art – technologies, including the use of various methods and tools of art.

- Problem-based educational technologies, when we explain a problem by offering a story (situation), during which children develop problem-solving skills in their own world. The child masters various types of activities aimed at learning to solve problems.

Work environment technology with objects

The environment in the gym and sports ground is created and improved taking into account the requirements of the Program applied in the preschool educational institution and the mental characteristics of children.

Students have the opportunity to be organized and act independently, which leads to a variety of physical activities.

Moving around the “zoned” space, the child learns to coordinate his movements and control his body.

The use of these technologies in the educational process helps to ensure emotional comfort and positive psychological well-being of the child in the process of communication with peers and adults in kindergarten and in the family, as well as the socio-emotional well-being of the child. environment in the world around him.

These technologies help children develop communication skills, develop research skills, and develop the ability to make optimal decisions in a given situation.

The use of computer presentations of educational portals when organizing educational activities with children on certain topics (“Winter and summer sports”, “Sports equipment for sports”) can certainly become an auxiliary tool for every guide.

The use of the above pedagogical technologies on an integrated basis and the implementation of modern requirements for the organization of the educational process in physical education and health work with preschool children allow us to come to the following conclusions:

1. improve the quality of pedagogical influence on children through the development of a comprehensive system of universally integrated knowledge, skills and abilities;
2. coordination of functional disorders of physical development, identification of preserved capabilities and individual abilities;
3. encouraging children to use the acquired knowledge and skills in independent motor activities related to their need for movement;
4. optimization of the load, taking into account the individual, psychological and age characteristics of preschoolers.

Preschool education technologies are designed to combine all methods into one, providing a comprehensive and effective educational process. It is the formation of the above skills and the use of these technologies in the activities of physical leaders that can help preschoolers develop the qualities necessary for them to get used to a new environment.

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